

A REVIEW ON SOLID DISPERSIONS MECHANISM OF SOLUBILITY IMPROVEMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION

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ABSTRACT

As an increasing proportion of drugs undergoing development are poorly water-soluble, solubilization technologies have become an essential feature in bringing them successfully to market. The solid dispersion is one such technology which in recent years has led to the approval of a large number of products, suggesting it is now the preferred technology for drug solubilization. However, despite considerable progress in understanding the nature of solid dispersions, many aspects of their behavior remain to be clarified such as the kinetics of phase separation in the solid state and in solution, and even such simple questions as how polymer molecular weight affects the drug crystallization rate. Research is also needed into the use of solid dispersions in conjunction with controlled release technologies such as the osmotic pump.

KEYWORDS: Solubilization Technologies, Solid Dispersion, Controlled Release etc.,

INTRODUCTION

The oral route of drug administration is the most common and preferred method of delivery due to convenience and ease of ingestion. From a patient's perspective, swallowing a dosage form is a comfortable and a familiar means of taking medication. As a result, patient compliance and hence drug treatment is typically more effective with orally administered medications as compared with other routes of administration, for example, parenteral.

The enhancement of oral bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs remains one of the most challenging aspects of drug development. Although salt formation, co-solubilization and particle size reduction have commonly been used to increase dissolution rate and thereby oral absorption and bioavailability of such drugs, there are practical limitations of these techniques. The salt formation technique is not feasible for neutral compounds and also the synthesis of appropriate salt forms of drugs that are weakly acidic or weakly basic may often not be practical. Even when salts can be prepared, an increased dissolution rate in the gastrointestinal tract may not be achieved in many cases because of the reversion of salts into aggregates of their respective acid or base forms. The solubilization of drugs in organic solvents or in aqueous media by the use of surfactants and cosolvents leads to liquid formulations that are usually undesirable from the viewpoints of patient acceptability and commercialization. Although particle size reduction is commonly used to increase dissolution rate, there is a practical limit to size reduction achieved by commonly used methods as controlled crystallization, grinding, pearl milling etc. The use of very fine powders in a dosage form may also be problematic because of handling difficulties and poor wettability due to charge development. In 1961, Sekiguchi and Obi developed a practical method whereby most of the limitations with the bioavailability enhancement of poorly water-soluble drugs can be overcome, which was termed as „Solid Dispersion“ [1-5].

From conventional capsules and tablets, the dissolution rate is limited by the size of the primary particles formed after disintegration of dosage forms. In this case, an average particle size of 5 µm is usually the lower limit, although higher particle sizes are

preferred for ease of handling, formulation and manufacturing. On the other hand, if a solid dispersion or a solid solution is used, a portion of the drug dissolves immediately to saturate the gastrointestinal fluid and the excess drug precipitates out as fine colloidal particles or oily globules of submicron size. Hence, due to promising increase in the bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs, solid dispersion has become one of the most active areas of research in the pharmaceutical field.

Definition and Types of Solid Dispersions:

Definition: Solid dispersion technology is the science of dispersing one or more active ingredients in an inert matrix in the solid stage to achieve an increased dissolution rate or sustained release of drug, altered solid state properties and improved stability [6].

Types of Solid Dispersions:

A) Simple Eutectic Mixture

B) Solid Solutions

Solid solution can generally be classified according to the extent of miscibility between the two components or the crystalline structure of the solid solution.

(i) Continuous solid solutions; (ii) Discontinuous solid solution; (iii) Substitutional solid solution; (iv) Interstitial solid solution

C) Glass Solution

D) Compound or Complex Formation

E) Amorphous Precipitation

Mechanism of Dissolution Rate Enhancement:

Corrigan reviewed the understanding of the mechanism of release from solid dispersion. The increase in drug dissolution rate from solid dispersion system can be attributed to a number of factors like particle size, crystalline or polymorphic forms and wettability of drug etc. It is very difficult to show experimentally that any one particular factor is more important than another. The main reasons postulated for the observed improvements in dissolution from these systems are as follows [7-9]:

a) Reduction of Particle Size:

In case of glass solution, solid solution and amorphous dispersions, particle size is reduced. This may result in enhanced dissolution rate due to increase in the surface area. Similarly, it has been suggested that the presentation of particles to dissolution medium as physically separate entities may reduce aggregation.

b) Solubilization Effect:

The carrier material, as it dissolves, may have a solubilization effect on the drug. Enhancement in solubility and

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dissolution rate of poorly soluble drugs is related to the ability of carrier matrix to improve local drug solubility as well as wettability.

c) Wettability and Dispersibility:

The carrier material may also have an enhancing effect on the wettability and dispersibility of the drug due to the surfactant action reducing the interfacial tension between hydrophobic drug particle and aqueous solvent phase, increasing the effective surface area exposed to the dissolution medium. This also retards agglomeration or aggregation of the particles, which can slow down the dissolution.

d) Conversion of Polymorphic Nature of Solute:

Energy required to transfer a molecule from crystal lattice of a purely crystalline solid is greater than that required for non-crystalline (amorphous) solid. Hence amorphous state of a substance shows higher dissolution rates. But the amorphous solids also demonstrate lack of physical stability due to natural tendency to form crystals. Thus formation of metastable dispersions with reduced lattice energy would result in faster dissolution rate and comparatively acceptable stability.

Selection of Carrier:

One of the most important steps in the formulation and development of solid dispersion for various applications is selection of carrier. The properties of carrier have a major influence on dissolution characteristics of the drug. A material should possess following characteristics to be suitable carrier for increasing dissolution [10].

- i. Freely water-soluble with intrinsic rapid dissolution properties
- ii. Non-toxic nature and pharmacologically inertness
- iii. Thermal stability preferably with low melting point especially for melt method
- iv. Solubility in a variety of solvents and should pass through a vitreous state upon solvent evaporation for the solvent method
- v. Ability to increase the aqueous solubility of the drug
- vi. Chemical compatibility and not forming a strongly bonded complex with drug.

Polymers used in Solid Dispersions:

A variety of polymers is offered as carriers for formulation of solid dispersion. Some polymers used in solid dispersions are as follows:

- A) Polyethylene Glycols (PEG)
- B) Polyvinyl Pyrrolidone (PVP)

- C) Polymers and Surface Active Agent Combinations
- D) Cyclodextrins
- E) Phospholipids

Methods of Preparation of Solid Dispersions:

Fusion Process:

The fusion process is technically less difficult method of preparing dispersions provided the drug and carrier are miscible in the molten state. Drug and carrier mixture of eutectic composition is molten at temperature above its eutectic temperature. Then molten mass is solidified on an ice bath and pulverized to a powder. Since a super saturation of the drug can be obtained by quenching the melt rapidly (when solute molecules are arrested in solvent matrix by instantaneous solidification), rapid congealing is favoured. The solidification is often performed on stainless steel plates to facilitate rapid heat loss. A modification of the process involves spray congealing from a modified spray drier onto cold metal surfaces.

Decomposition should be avoided during fusion but is often dependent on composition and affected by fusion time, temperature and rate of cooling. Therefore, to maintain drug content and physicochemical stability of formulation at an acceptable level, fusion must be effected at a temperature only just in excess of that which completely melts both drug and carrier [11,12].

Solvent Evaporation Process:

Solid dispersion prepared by solvent removal process was termed by Bates et al. as "Cocprecipitates". But these systems should more correctly, be designated as „Coevaporate“, a term that has been recently adopted.

The solvent evaporation process uses organic solvents, the agent to intimately mix the drug and carrier molecules and was initially used by Tachibana and Nakamura, where, chloroform was used to co-dissolve β-carotene and PVP to form Co-evaporate.

The choice of solvent and its removal rate are critical parameters affecting the quality of the solid dispersion. Since the chosen carriers are generally hydrophilic and the drugs are hydrophobic, the selection of a common solvent is difficult and its complete removal, necessitated by its toxic nature, is imperative. Vacuum evaporation may be used for solvent removal at low temperature and also at a controlled rate. More rapid removal of the solvent may be accomplished by freeze-drying. The difficulties in selecting a common solvent to both drug and carrier may be overcome by using an azeotropic mixture of solvent in water.

Fig. 1: Pharmaceutical Applications of Solid Dispersion

Fusion Solvent Method:

This method consists of dissolving the drug in a suitable solvent and incorporating the solution directly in the melt of

carrier. If the carrier is capable of holding a certain proportion of liquid yet maintains its solid properties and if the liquid is innocuous, then the need for solvent removal is eliminated. This

method is particularly useful for drugs that have high melting points or they are thermo-labile.

Supercritical Fluid Process:

Supercritical CO₂ is a good solvent for water-insoluble as well as water-soluble compounds under suitable conditions of temperature and pressure. Therefore, it has potential as an alternative for conventional organic solvents used in solvent based processes for forming solid dispersions due to its favorable properties of being non-toxic and inexpensive. The process consists of the following steps:

- i. Charging the bioactive material and suitable polymer into the autoclave.
- ii. Addition of supercritical CO₂ under precise conditions of temperature and pressure, that causes polymer to swell
- iii. Mechanical stirring in the autoclave
- iv. Rapid depressurization of the autoclave vessel through a computer controlled orifice to obtain desired particle size.

The temperature condition used in this process is fairly mild (35-75°C), which allows handling of heat sensitive biomolecules, such as enzymes and proteins.

Characterization of Solid Dispersion

A. Detection of crystallinity in solid dispersions:

Several different molecular structures of the drug in the matrix can be encountered in solid dispersions.

Many attempts have been made to investigate the molecular arrangement in solid dispersions. However, most effort has been put into differentiate between amorphous and crystalline material. For that purpose many techniques are available which detect the amount of crystalline material in the dispersion. The amount of amorphous material is never measured directly but is mostly derived from the amount of crystalline material in the sample. It should be noted that through the assessment of crystallinity as method to determine the amount of amorphous drug it will not be revealed whether the drug is present as amorphous drug particles or as molecularly dispersed molecules^[13].

The following techniques are available to detect (the degree of) crystallinity

1. Powder X-ray diffraction can be used to qualitatively detect material with long range order. Sharper diffraction peaks indicate more crystalline material. Recently developed X-ray equipment is semi-quantitative.
2. Infrared spectroscopy (IR) can be used to detect the variation in the energy distribution of interactions between drug and matrix. Sharp vibrational bands indicate crystallinity. Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to accurately detect crystallinities ranging from 1 to 99% in pure material. However in solid dispersions only qualitative detection was possible.
3. Water vapour sorption can be used to discriminate between amorphous and crystalline material when the hygroscopicity is different. This method requires accurate data on the hygroscopicity of both completely crystalline and completely amorphous samples.
4. Isothermal Microcalorimetry measures the crystallization energy of amorphous material that is heated above its glass transition temperature (T_g). However, this technique has some limitations. Firstly, this technique can only be applied if the physical stability is such that only during the measurement crystallization takes place. Secondly, it has to be assumed that all amorphous material crystallizes. Thirdly, in a binary mixture of two amorphous compounds a distinction between crystallization energies of drug and matrix is difficult.
5. Dissolution Calorimetry measures the energy of dissolution, which is dependent on the crystallinity of the sample. Usually, dissolution of crystalline material is endothermic, whereas dissolution of amorphous material is exothermic.
6. Macroscopic techniques that measure mechanical properties that are different for amorphous and crystalline material can be indicative for the degree of crystallinity. Density measurements and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

determine the modulus of elasticity and viscosity and thus affected by the degree of crystallinity. However, also these techniques require knowledge about the additivity of these properties in intimately mixed binary solids.

7. A frequently used technique to detect the amount of crystalline material is Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). In DSC, samples are heated with a constant heating rate and the amount of energy necessary for that is detected. With DSC the temperatures at which thermal events occur can be detected. Thermal events can be a glass to rubber transition, (re)crystallization, melting or degradation. Furthermore, the melting- and (re)crystallization energy can be quantified. The melting energy can be used to detect the amount of crystalline material. Possibly, the recrystallization energy can be used to calculate the amount of amorphous material provided, that all amorphous material is transformed to the crystalline state. If during DSC-measurements, amorphous material crystallizes, information is obtained on the crystallization kinetics and on the physical stability of the amorphous sample.

To quantify the amount of crystalline material, measurements should be completed before crystallization of amorphous material has started. In some cases, this can be established applying high scanning rates.

B. Detection of molecular structure in amorphous solid dispersions:

The properties of a solid dispersion are highly affected by the uniformity of the distribution of the drug in the matrix. The stability and dissolution behaviour could be different for solid dispersions that do not contain any crystalline drug particles, i.e. solid dispersions of type V and VI or for type II and III. However, not only the Knowledge on the physical state (crystalline or amorphous) is important; the distribution of the drug as amorphous or crystalline particles or as separate drug molecules is relevant to the properties of the solid dispersion too. Nevertheless, only very few studies focus on the discrimination between amorphous incorporated particles versus molecular distribution or homogeneous mixtures.

1. Confocal Raman Spectroscopy was used to measure the homogeneity of the solid mixture of ibuprofen in PVP (Breitenbach et al., 1999). It was described that a standard deviation in drug content smaller than 10% was indicative of homogeneous distribution. Because of the pixel size of 2 μm³, uncertainty remains about the presence of nano-sized amorphous drug particles.
2. Using IR or FTIR, the extent of interactions between drug and matrix can be measured. The interactions are indicative for the mode of incorporation of the drug, because separately dispersed drug molecules will have more drug-matrix interactions than when the drug is present in amorphous clusters or other multi-molecule arrangements.
3. Temperature Modulated Differential Scanning Calorimetry (TMDSC) can be used to assess the degree of mixing of an incorporated drug. Due to the modulation, reversible and irreversible events can be separated. For example, glass transitions (reversible) are separated from crystallization or relaxation (irreversible) in amorphous materials. Furthermore, the value of the T_g is a function of the composition of the homogeneously mixed solid dispersion. It has been shown that the sensitivity of TMDSC is higher than conventional DSC. Therefore this technique can be used to assess the amount of molecularly dispersed drug, and from that the fraction of drug that is dispersed as separate molecules is calculated.

In-vitro Release:

Release of API from an SD may be studied by a variety of in-vitro methods. One way to evaluate release from SDs is by simple powder dissolution. This is performed by transferring a known mass of material into a known volume of biologically relevant dissolution medium (e.g. simulated gastric/intestinal fluid) under constant stirring. Solution concentrations are measured as a function of time to generate a concentration versus time release profile for the API. Solution concentrations in significant excess of the equilibrium API solubility in the particular medium should be targeted to test the ability of the SD to achieve and maintain supersaturation. However, it is desirable to be as biorelevant as possible to predict in-vivo performance. More dynamic

techniques, such as the artificial stomach duodenum, and other multicompartamental dissolution/ release methods, should be employed to understand API release from SDs. These methods are used to understand complex release phenomena and to begin building in-vitro/in-vivo correlations. A dynamic dilution scheme reported by Gao et al, was recently shown to provide valuable inputs for predictions of pharmacokinetics (PK) [14].

FUTURE PROSPECTS

Despite many advantages of solid dispersion, issues related to preparation, reproducibility, formulation, scale up and stability has limited its use in commercial dosage forms for poorly water-soluble drugs. Successful development of solid dispersion systems for preclinical, clinical and commercial use has been feasible in recent years due to the availability of surface active and self-emulsifying carriers with relatively low melting points. The preparation of dosage forms involves the solubilization of drug in melted carriers and the filling of the hot solutions into hard gelatin capsules because of the simplicity of manufacturing and scale-up processes, the physicochemical properties and as a result, the bioavailability of solid dispersions are not expected to change significantly during the scale-up. For this reason, the popularity of the solid dispersion system to solve difficult bioavailability issues of poorly water-soluble drugs will grow rapidly. As the dosage form can be developed and prepared using small amount of drug substance in early stages of the drug development process, the system might have an advantage over such other commonly used bioavailability enhancement techniques such as micronization and soft gelatin encapsulation.

Research should also be directed towards identification and synthesis of new possibilities of vehicles or excipients that would retard or prevent crystallization of drugs from super-saturated systems. Attention must be given to any physiological, pharmacological and toxicological effects of carriers.

In addition to bioavailability enhancement, much recent efforts and advances in the research on solid dispersion systems are directed towards the development of extended release dosage forms.

Physical and chemical stability of both drug and carrier in a solid dispersion are major developmental issues, so future research needs to be directed to address various stability issues. The semisolid and waxy nature of solid dispersions poses unique stability problem that might not be seen in other types of solid dosage forms. Predictive methods are necessary for the investigation of any potential drug crystallization and its impact on dissolution and bioavailability. Also possible drug-carrier interactions must also be investigated.

CONCLUSION

Solid dispersions have attracted considerable interest as an efficient means of improving the dissolution rate and hence the bioavailability of a range of hydrophobic drugs. This article reviews the various preparation techniques for solid dispersion and compiles some of the recent technology transfers. The different types of solid dispersions based on the molecular arrangement

have been highlighted. Some of the practical aspects to be considered for the preparation of solid dispersions, such as selection of carrier and methods of physicochemical characterization, along with an insight into the molecular arrangement of drugs in solid dispersions are also discussed. Finally, an in-depth rationale for limited commercialization of solid dispersions and recent revival has been considered.

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